

	chr	pos (hg38)	LD (r ²)	LD (r ²)	variant	Ref	Alt	AFR freq	AMR freq	ASN freq	EUR freq	SiPhy cons	Promoter histone marks	Enhancer histone marks	DNase	Proteins bound	Motifs changed	NHGRI/EBI GWAS hits	GRASP QTL hits	Selected eQTL hits	GENCODE genes	RefSeq genes	dbSNP func annot
rs744154	16	13921224	1	1	rs744154	G	C	0.16	0.14	0.27	0.25		17 tissues	17 tissues	6 tissues		Smad			3 hits	ERCC4	ERCC4	intronic
rs2296147	3	102846025	1	1	rs2296147	T	C	0.17	0.38	0.19	0.44		24 tissues		53 tissues	17 bound proteins	BDP1			9 hits	ERCC5	BIVM-ERCC5	5'-UTR
rs17655	13	102875652	1	1	rs17655	G	C	0.5	0.27	0.49	0.26			ESDR, BRN			DEC,GR,Nkx2		1 hit	20 hits	ERCC5	BIVM-ERCC5	missense
rs751402	13	102845848	1	1	rs751402	A	G	0.67	0.7	0.63	0.8		24 tissues		53 tissues	48 bound proteins	E2F,IRC900814,Pou3f2			3 hits	ERCC5	BIVM-ERCC5	5'-UTR

Variant	Gene	Position ^a	Annotation	Promoter histone marks ^b	Enhancer histone marks ^c	DNase ^d	Proteins bound ^e	Motifs changed ^f
rs744154	ERCC4	13921224	intronic	17 tissues	17 tissues	6 tissues		Smad
rs2296147	ERCC5	102846025	5'-UTR	24 tissues		53 tissues	17 bound proteins	BDP1
rs17655	ERCC5	102875652	missense		ESDR, BRN			DEC,GR,Nkx2
rs751402	ERCC5	102845848	5'-UTR	24 tissues		53 tissues	48 bound proteins	E2F,IRC900814,Pou3f2

^aThe chromosome position is based on NCBI Build 37

^bHistone modification of H3K4me1 and H3K27ac (tissue types: if >3, only the number is included).

^cHistone modification of H3K4me3 (tissue types: if >3, only the number is included)

^dLevels of DNase I hypersensitivity (tissue types: if >3, only the number is included).

^eAlteration in transcription factor binding (disruptions: if >3, only the number is included)

^fAlteration in regulatory motif (disruptions: if >3, only the number is included).